

The Analysis of Sustainability Indices of Multi-actor Communities of Practices

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Abstract

One of the strategies implemented by the UPSCALE project to address food insecurity, livelihoods, and climate change resilience in Eastern Africa was the development of a platform to incorporate local, national, and international partners. The Multi-actor Communities (MACs) were established to enable effective and efficient transdisciplinary and multi-actor research and technology intervention to enhance the coordination of information sharing and transdisciplinary knowledge exchange among clusters of stakeholders. After a three-year project period, a survey was conducted to assess the sustainability of MACs. Four indices were adopted, including the interest, impact, benefits, and conflict levels of the MACs in the PPT value chain. The findings indicated either very high or high levels of interest, benefits, and impact, and low conflict among the MACs. This showed a high probability of MAC sustainability beyond the project period. Based on the indices, the PCA scores showed a high sustainability index for each of the countries. Additionally, an increase in the years the MACs have in agro-technology sector increased the sustainability index by 18.7%. Therefore, from the evidence of the sustainability potential of MACs, the study recommends the inclusion of MACs in the regional policies for implementing new technologies in various sectors.

Key words: Push-Pull Technology; UPSCALE project; MAC; Interest rating; Impact rating; Benefits rating; Conflict levels; Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of UPSCALE was to address food insecurity, improve livelihoods, and enhance climate change resilience in East Africa (EA), while reducing the environmental impact of agricultural practices. To achieve this, the project was designed to use PPT as an integrated agro-ecological practice. PPT is a farming practice that integrates fodder production into cereal farming to reduce the infestation of pests and weeds, such as the fall armyworm and striga weed, which have reduced productivity among farmers in the EA. PPT farming plots are established with Nappier/*brachiaria* grass on the borders of the main crop (cereal/vegetables) and *desmodium* between the rows of the main crop, as shown in Figure 1 (Cheruiyot et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2011, 2018). This enhances climate-resilient and sustainable agricultural intensification.

Figure 1: source <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.3763/ijas.2010.0558>

One of the crucial strategies of the UPSCALE project was to develop a platform that incorporates local, national, and international partners to identify and target suitable areas and methods for stimulating PPT adoption, expansion, and adaptation beyond the project's scope through stakeholders at all levels of academia, government, and private entities.

The WP1 in the project focused on creating an enabling environment for effective and efficient transdisciplinary and multi-actor research and technology intervention to coordinate information sharing and transdisciplinary knowledge exchange among stakeholders. The WP

led the formation of MACs, organizing stakeholder collaborative events, instigating public-private partnerships to improve farmers' timely access to agricultural input and output markets, stimulating links to other agricultural services, and supporting participative and transdisciplinary approaches within the project and other networks.

The main goals were to coordinate and create synergies with ongoing projects on sustainable intensification in Africa; form MACs of practice for effective transdisciplinary collaboration and participatory research among UPSCALE stakeholders in planning, programming and implementation of activities; strengthen the functional linkage between UPSCALE research and innovation activities and farmers, policy and value chain-oriented extension officers; build networks supporting advocacy for an enabling policy environment for institutional dissemination and adoption of the PPT; and identify 'best practices' for transformative transdisciplinary research in service of sustainable intensification.

One of the tasks in WP1 was the formation of MACs for upscaling PPT in EA. The MACs were based on existing and new networks in each country, integrating the wide clusters of stakeholders that were already collaborating with UPSCALE partners across the value chain. MACs were linked to existing platforms, networks, and ongoing projects. Each MAC had a management coordination team for UPSCALE activities and a planned schedule of activities based on yearly workshops.

The MACs responsibility was organizing national and regional workshops, bringing together MAC members including UPSCALE partners, research and extension, government and value chain actors from farming, the public, business, and policy formulators to raise awareness on transdisciplinary research; support sustainable commercial linkages among stakeholders on PPT value chains; form participative ground for policy briefs on PPT adoption strategy, support advocacy efforts for an enabling policy environment, identify gaps and necessary changes under UPSCALE project objectives, issues of scale of implementation, and updating and revising the project implementation and impact pathways based on indicators and outcomes of monitoring, evaluation, and Sharing tasks.

Therefore, after three years of the project, a stakeholder analysis was conducted on the sustainability of established MACs in all African partner countries based on interest, impact, benefits, and conflict levels among MACs. The analysis of the MACs considered the iterative process of obtaining information about the available partners in MAC, the actors' impact, individually and collectively, and also how the actors are impacted by the project's instruments

and activities of conceptualization, inception, presentation, adoption, practice, advocacy, dissemination, outreach, monitoring, and evaluation during and beyond the project cycle. The analysis further evaluated gender issues, youth participation, and stakeholders' experiences in agro-technology projects.

Theoretical framework

The stochastic utility model theory was employed to establish the four indicators used in assessing the sustainability of the MAC. The theory holds that the adoption and sustainability of a technology are based on the utility derived. Therefore, utility is achieved when the interests of adopters are met, the technology has an optimal impact, both qualitative and quantitative benefits are observed, and conflicts with other existing technologies are minimal. Therefore, the same principle was applied to the willingness of farmers to engage in the MACs based on the benefits, interests, impacts, and conflicts that can arise among the stakeholders.

METHODOLOGY

The study design

Based on the stakeholders' engagement and discussions from WP1 in the UPSCALE project, the need to assess the sustainability of PPT emerged. Thereafter, a tool was designed, sent to the country coordinators, and later used to gather data from various stakeholders in the UPSCALE project in 2023. The study targeted all the stakeholders along the PPT products value chain. This included the research organizations, government institutions, financial institutions, extension officers, PPT farmers, agro dealers, transporters, aggregators, processors, and consumers of PPT products. The output was then presented at the national MAC meetings in each country for validation and refinement. Thereafter, the data were used for the UPSCALE project reporting on the state of MAC sustainability.

The study area

The study was conducted in five Eastern African countries, including Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Rwanda, and Ethiopia. The study area is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Study area map; source:

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326293832/figure/fig1/AS:669416220016665@1536612672730/Map-of-Africa-showing-countries-Ethiopia-Uganda-Kenya-and-Tanzania-with-incidences-of.png>

Data analysis

The study employed descriptive statistics to summarize the frequency of respondents according to the indicators assessed (interest, impact, benefit, and conflict levels in MACs). The scale of assessment was 1 to 5, representing very low, low, moderate, high, and very high levels. The percentage frequency was also presented. Principal Component Analysis was adopted to establish the sustainability index for each country and for the region. A multiple regression model was also adopted to evaluate the effects of age, experience, and gender on MACs sustainability.

RESULTS

Only 5 females and 4 males participated in the Kenyan MAC Stakeholder Analysis. The stakeholders included financial institutions, research institutions, and farmer groups. The majority of stakeholders were from financial and research institutions. The analysis showed that the years of experience of stakeholders in MACs ranged from 2 to 14 years, with an average of 8 years. The sustainable indices assessed include the Interest, impact, Benefit, and Conflict levels of the stakeholders in MACs as presented in Table 1. The results indicate a very high level of interest and benefits, a high impact, and a low conflict within the established MACs. Additionally, the results suggest a higher number of youth participants than adults.

Table 1: Kenya MAC Stakeholders' Rating Constructs (n=9)

Rating	AV. Rate	Percentage	Interpretation
Interest Rating	5	81.3%	Very High
Impact Rating	4	68.8%	High
Benefit Rating	5	87.5%	Very High
Conflict Rating	1	81.3%	Very Low
Value proposition			
Gender (<i>Female: Male</i>)	5:04	9	
Age-set: (<i>Youth: Active Adults: Senior Adults</i>)	5:03:01	9	
Average Experience in Agro Tech. Projects	8		
Average Age of the MAC members	38		

The PCA score results were also 83%. This shows a high sustainability index of MACs in Kenya.

```
. pca Interest_Rating Impact_Rating Benefit_Rating Conflict_Rating
```

```
Principal components/correlation          Number of obs   =          9
                                           Number of comp. =          4
                                           Trace           =          4
Rotation: (unrotated = principal)        Rho             =       1.0000
```

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	2.30431	1.26305	0.5761	0.5761
Comp2	1.04126	.661752	0.2603	0.8364
Comp3	.379505	.104576	0.0949	0.9313
Comp4	.274929	.	0.0687	1.0000

In the Rwanda MAC Stakeholder Analysis, 15% of the participants were female and 85% male. The stakeholders included were; Ministry of Agriculture, recommended for their impact in value chain policies and integration; Rwanda Agriculture Board which is a Research and Extension officers and an UPSCALE partner, recommended for their role in value chain extension and mobilization; Gatsibo District led by Director of Agriculture and Animal Resources, working on policy advocacy, project implementation, and extension; Food for the Hungry, the Rwandan UPSCALE national coordinator that is involved in project implementation, mobilization, and coordination; University of Rwanda, a higher education institution involved in research and dissemination of findings; Farmers Cooperatives dealing with policy advocacy and advisory services; Imbaraga Farmers Federation a project implementation federation; Bank of Kigali that offers agricultural finance; 9) Radiant Insurance that is involved in value chain finance and marketing; Agra Care Limited and Kenya Seed Company, Rwanda engaged in the dissemination of project information and agro-dealership of agricultural inputs; Rwanda Development Organization and Adecor, involved in policy engagement, stakeholder networks and advisory; and Rebero Media Limited, a media group, engaged in broadcasting, dissemination, and communication of project information. The

sustainable indices assessed include the interest, impact, benefit, and conflict levels of the stakeholders in PPT farming as presented in Table 2. The results indicate a very high level of interest and benefits, a high impact, and a low conflict within the formed MACs. Additionally, the results suggest that youth are more involved in the MACs than adults. The average age of stakeholders was 34 years, with an average of 10 years of experience in agro-technology projects.

Table 2: Rwanda MAC Stakeholders' Rating Constructs (n=20)

Rating	AV. Rate	Percentage	Interpretation
Interest Rating	4	95%	Very High
Impact Rating	5	75%	High
Benefit Rating	5	100%	Very High
Conflict Rating	1	100%	Very Low
Value proposition			
Gender (<i>Female: Male</i>)	3:17	20	
Age-set: (<i>Youth: Active Adults: Senior Adults</i>)	15:05:00	20	
Average Experience in Agro Tech. Projects	10		
Average Age of the MAC members	34		

The PCA score showed that the sustainability index of MACs in Rwanda is over 69%.

```
. pca Interest_Rating Impact_Rating Benefit_Rating Conflict_Rating
(Benefit_Rating dropped because of zero variance)
(Conflict_Rating dropped because of zero variance)
```

```
Principal components/correlation          Number of obs   =      20
                                           Number of comp. =       2
                                           Trace           =       2
Rotation: (unrotated = principal)        Rho              =     1.0000
```

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	1.39736	.794719	0.6987	0.6987
Comp2	.60264	.	0.3013	1.0000

Only 3 females and 15 males participated in the Ethiopia MAC Stakeholder Analysis. The results indicate that most stakeholders have over 15 years of experience, demonstrating expertise and knowledge. The Ethiopian MAC comprises diverse stakeholders representing key facets of the nation's agricultural value chain. Its membership includes representatives from governmental bodies like the Ministry of Agriculture, non-governmental organizations including PELUM Ethiopia and PAN, agricultural research institutes, institutions of higher learning, financial institutions, and farmer representatives. The sustainable indices assessed include the Interest, impact, Benefit, and Conflict levels of the stakeholders in the MACs as presented in Table 3. The results indicate a very high level of impact and benefits, a high

interest, and a low conflict within the MACs. Additionally, the results show higher youth engagement in the MACs than in adults. The ages of the stakeholders ranged from 27 to 62, with an average experience of 13 years in agro technology projects.

Table 3: Ethiopia MAC Stakeholders' Rating Constructs (n=18)

Rating	AV. Rate	Percentage	Interpretation
Interest Rating	4	61.1%	High
Impact Rating	5	83.3%	Very High
Benefit Rating	5	100%	Very High
Conflict Rating	1	100%	Very Low
Value proposition			
Gender (<i>Female: Male</i>)	3:15	18	
Age-set: (<i>Youth: Active Adults: Senior Adults</i>)	7:08:03	18	
Average Experience in Agro Tech. Projects	13		
Average Age of the MAC members	27-62		

The PCA score showed that the sustainability index of MACs in Ethiopia is over 64%

```
. pca Interest_Rating Impact_Rating Benefit_Rating Conflict_Rating
(Benefit_Rating dropped because of zero variance)
(Conflict_Rating dropped because of zero variance)
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```
Principal components/correlation          Number of obs =      18
                                           Number of comp. =     2
                                           Trace =              2
Rotation: (unrotated = principal)        Rho =               1.0000
```

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	1.28	.56	0.6400	0.6400
Comp2	.72	.	0.3600	1.0000

In the Tanzania MAC Stakeholder Analysis, 7 females and 22 males participated. The stakeholders engaged were highly affiliated with research institutions, followed by government agencies, then faith-based organizations, and finally financial institutions. The sustainable indices assessed include the Interest, impact, Benefit, and Conflict levels of the stakeholders in the established MACs as presented in Table 4. The results indicate a very high level of interest, high benefits and impact, and a low conflict within the MACs. Additionally, the results indicate that more youth engaged in MACs than adults. The experience of stakeholders in agro technology projects was 6 years, and the average age of the MAC members was between 36 and 55.

Table 4: Tanzania MAC Stakeholders' Rating Constructs (n=29)

Rating	AV. Rate	Percentage	Interpretation
Interest Rating	5	62.1%	Very High
Impact Rating	4	79.3%	High
Benefit Rating	4	75.9%	High
Conflict Rating	1	82.8%	Very Low
Value proposition			
Gender (<i>Female: Male</i>)	7:22	29	
Age-set: (<i>Youth: Active Adults: Senior Adults</i>)	13:12:03	29	
Average Experience in Agro Tech. Projects	6		
Average Age of the MAC members	36-55		

The PCA score showed that the sustainability index of MACs in Tanzania is over 60%

```
. pca Interest_Rating Impact_Rating Benefit_Rating Conflict_Rating
Principal components/correlation      Number of obs =      29
                                      Number of comp. =      4
                                      Trace =      4
Rotation: (unrotated = principal)    Rho =      1.0000
```

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	1.37245	.342685	0.3431	0.3431
Comp2	1.02977	.0759273	0.2574	0.6006
Comp3	.95384	.309901	0.2385	0.8390
Comp4	.643939	.	0.1610	1.0000

In the Uganda MAC Stakeholder Analysis, 1 female and 9 males participated. The majority of the stakeholders play various roles in the PPT value chain, such as extension officers, agricultural technologists, financiers, aggregators, farmers, farming system experts, and media representatives. The sustainable indices assessed include the Interest, Impact, Benefit, and Conflict levels within MACs as presented in Table 5. The results indicate very high levels of interest, a high impact and benefits, and a low conflict within the established MACs. Additionally, the results show that the youth were many among the stakeholders with low engagement of adults. Of all the MAC members, 60% fall in the range of 36-55, while 18-35 and 56 and above each take up 20 percent

Table 5: Uganda MAC Stakeholders' Rating Constructs (n=10)

Rating	AV. Rate	Percentage	Interpretation
Interest Rating	5	100%	Very High
Impact Rating	4	75%	High
Benefit Rating	4	66.7%	High
Conflict Rating	1	100%	Very Low
Value proposition			
Gender (<i>Female: Male</i>)	1:09	10	
Age-set: (<i>Youth: Active Adults: Senior Adults</i>)	2:08:00	10	
Average Experience in Agro Tech. Projects	10		
Average Age of the MAC members	29-60		

The PCA score showed that the sustainability index of MACs in Uganda is over 64%

```
. pca Interest_Rating Impact_Rating Benefit_Rating Conflict_Rating
(Interest_Rating dropped because of zero variance)
(Conflict_Rating dropped because of zero variance)
```

```
Principal components/correlation          Number of obs   =      10
                                           Number of comp. =       2
                                           Trace           =       2
Rotation: (unrotated = principal)        Rho              =     1.0000
```

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	1.28365	.567309	0.6418	0.6418
Comp2	.716346	.	0.3582	1.0000

The results also indicate that the sustainability index of MACs in all countries combined is above 40%

```
. pca Interest_Rating Impact_Rating Benefit_Rating Conflict_Rating
```

```
Principal components/correlation          Number of obs   =      86
                                           Number of comp. =       4
                                           Trace           =       4
Rotation: (unrotated = principal)        Rho              =     1.0000
```

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	1.71454	.778181	0.4286	0.4286
Comp2	.93636	.191391	0.2341	0.6627
Comp3	.744969	.140838	0.1862	0.8490
Comp4	.604131	.	0.1510	1.0000

Figure 3: Country rating

Gender and Age Set Analysis

The results also show that age and the farmers' experience in agro-technology influence the perceived sustainability of MACs.

```
. reg pc1 Age Experience_AgroTech_Years gender1
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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	86
Model	38.2142253	3	12.7380751	F(3, 82)	=	9.71
Residual	107.521756	82	1.31124092	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Total	145.735981	85	1.71454096	R-squared	=	0.2622
				Adj R-squared	=	0.2352
				Root MSE	=	1.1451

	pc1	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
Age		-.039212	.0156437	-2.51	0.014	-.0703324 -.0080917
Experience_AgroTech_Years		.1873064	.0445135	4.21	0.000	.0987549 .2758579
gender1		.2117285	.2979172	0.71	0.479	-.3809236 .8043807
_cons		-.3958862	.9602841	-0.41	0.681	-2.306197 1.514425

The gender of the MAC members does not influence sustainability. The results show that an increase in age by a year reduces the perceived MAC sustainability index by 3.9%. When the experience in the MACs in agro-technology increases by one year, the sustainability index increases by 18.7%.

DISCUSSION

The high engagement of financial institutions in Kenyan stakeholder analysis indicates an opportunity for financial institutions to provide incentives and credit to farmers for the upscaling of PPT and support other MAC members who may be financially constrained. An average of 8 years of experience in agro technology projects showed that stakeholders had adequate knowledge, skills, and extension experience in coordinating the MACs for sustainability. The high levels of interest, impact, and benefits of PPT, characterized by low conflict, could also be attributed to high collaboration among the stakeholders, the ability to integrate MACs into existing farming systems in the region, the high yields associated with PPT as a result of MACs, and the agroecological gains that farmers derive. The results align with the literature on PPT (Khan et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2020; Pickett et al., 2014). In the findings, the researchers reported a high interest in PPT farming due to increased forage production, control of striga weed, and conservation of biodiversity as the benefits. The high number of youth engagement in MACs could be associated with the financial incentives, quick rewards, and the initiatives of MACs in disseminating PPT information.

The Rwanda Stakeholder Analysis indicated that males are dominating the MACs. Therefore, there is a need for deliberate effort to recruit more women in both the management structure of the MAC and the operating platform, in keeping with the goals of the UPSCALE project. However, a diverse range of stakeholders participated. This could be associated with the initiative of MACs in networking with new networks to enhance the PPT farming system. There was also very high interest and benefits, a high impact, and a low conflict level in the MACs, which showed that the stakeholders are willing to engage and participate in MACs to enhance product value chains. This would enhance MAC sustainability. The results also indicated a high youth participation in the MACs. This could be associated with high incentives and the improved productivity potential of PPT farming. These results align with the literature (Fischler, 2010; icipe, 2015; Khan et al., 2016). In the reports, the incentives from PPT farming of reducing pests, diseases, and weeds, increasing farm output, and maintaining soil fertility have enhanced interest in participating, especially among women and youth.

The low female engagement in Ethiopia's MAC Stakeholder Analysis could be associated with the low dissemination of PPT information. This calls for the active involvement of women in PPT farming as well as in the MAC structures. However, high experience of stakeholders in the agro-technology project demonstrated a pool of skills that established MACs can leverage. The involvement of the government suggests the possibility of integrating MACs in national agricultural strategies as a technology dissemination platform. The youth engagement in MACs also showed a sense of sustainability. There was also high interest, impact, and benefits from the established MACs. The results agree with some of the findings in the literature (Nyangau et al., 2018).

According to the Tanzanian Stakeholder Analysis, there is a need to engage more women in MACs. This could be done through road shows, workshops, and farmer training. The results also indicated a very high interest, high benefits, and impact, as well as a low conflict level of PPT farming within the MACs, which is associated with the returns from PPT farming. The youth engagement could also be a result of employment opportunities along the value chain. The findings align with the literature (Cheruiyot et al., 2022; Chidawanyika et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2008). In the reports, the ability of PPT to maintain soil fertility, increase productivity, support dairy farming, and reduce the need for external farm inputs has generated a high interest among farmers to participate.

Similarly, in Uganda, stakeholder analysis showed that male participants dominated. This could be attributed to the greater willingness of men to adopt new technologies compared to women. Men are generally more inclined to take risks than women. The results also showed a very high level of interest, a significant impact, and benefits, as well as a low level of conflict among the established MACs. This was attributed to the good performance of PPT products, the preservation of soil fertility, and the resulting agroecological benefits. However, youth engagement in the MACs was low, possibly due to limited dissemination of information on PPT and low participation in agricultural projects.

The sustainability index of MACs was also positively influenced by the experience in agro-technology industry. This could be attributed to the knowledge and skills that the MACs gain in the sectors over time. Therefore, for the sustainability of MACs, it is necessary to leverage on the coordination and collaboration with other established networks and platforms. The linkage of MACs to those networks has a potential to enhance sustainability.

CONCLUSION

The study objective was to assess the sustainability of MACs based on interest, benefits, impact levels, and conflict levels as the indices. The results indicate very high or high interest levels of benefits, impact, and low conflict among stakeholders within the established MACs in all 5 countries assessed. This indicated that the stakeholders are willing to continue participating in the activities of MACs along the PPT products value chain. A low conflict level or lack of conflicting interests within the MACs shows a high level of collaboration among the stakeholders. Therefore, this makes MAC a platform for technology transfer, especially where new technologies are involved. It was also realized that MAC members experience in agro-technology industry is crucial in enhancing the sustainability index. Since MACs have shown the potential of being sustainable in UPSCALE project, it was therefore, concluded that it should be included in the regional policies and be in cooperated in other projects that are transferring new technology to the people. The strength of MAC is in the stakeholders' collaboration and coordination along the entire value system.

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